

STAND: MARCH 2025¹

Guidelines for the standardised designation of affiliation in scientific publications

Affiliation guidelines of the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin

**Museum für Naturkunde Berlin
Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Research**

¹ Following the decision of the Management Board and the Directorate General on 25.03.2025

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Preamble

The "Museum für Naturkunde – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science" is one of the leading research institutions for evolution and biodiversity worldwide. As a research museum and communication centre, it actively contributes to the global scientific and societal dialogue about the future of the Earth and enhances the international visibility and reputation of the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin through its renowned publications.

In order to optimally highlight the scientific achievements of researchers, a standardised designation of institutional affiliation is essential. A uniform affiliation designation ensures that publications can be clearly attributed to the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin, providing the basis for precise recognition in international comparisons.

A correct affiliation guarantees the accurate representation of the research accomplishments of individual scientists and increases the visibility of the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin. It also facilitates the securing of funding and is essential for the creation of reports and statistical analyses.

This guideline applies to all scientific publications in which the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin is involved. It is mandatory and must be followed in all publications, as well as in any context where the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin is mentioned (e. g. on posters, in lectures and presentations, or in grant applications).

The publication guideline complements the existing policies and guidelines of the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin: the Guideline on Good Scientific Practice, the Open Access Policy 2025-2030, the Data Guideline on Handling Research Data, and the Guideline on Copyright Attribution for Media and Data from Collection Enrichment.

1. Scope

This Affiliation Guideline applies to all members of the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin, whether they hold scientific or non-scientific positions. This includes permanent staff, doctoral candidates and students, visiting researchers, and other individuals involved in research projects or scientific contributions at the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin.

Only publications that comply with the correct affiliation requirements will be considered for internal funding and Open Access support.

2. Standardised Designation of the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin

The name "Museum für Naturkunde Berlin" is treated as a proper noun and is not translated into other languages. The institutional affiliation in scientific publications should be cited as follows:

Long version (German): *"Museum für Naturkunde - Leibniz-Institut für Evolutions- und Biodiversitätsforschung"*

Long version (English): *"Museum für Naturkunde – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science"*

2.1. Name variants and abbreviations

If there is a character limit imposed by the publisher, the standardised short form should be:

Short version (German and English): Museum für Naturkunde Berlin

Abbreviations such as "MfN" are not permitted.

2.2. Designation of Departments or Research Groups

If a specific department or research group needs to be mentioned, it should also be included to ensure proper attribution within the institution:

Example: Museum für Naturkunde - Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science, Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Discovery

Affiliation with a research cluster, etc., should not be included in the affiliation but rather in the acknowledgments section.

2.3. Address Information

The general postal address of the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin should be used. Private addresses should not be used as contact addresses. The addition of the country designation "Germany" or "Deutschland" is recommended for international publications, as shown below:

Example: Museum für Naturkunde - Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science, Invalidenstraße 43, 10115 Berlin, Germany

2.4. Email Address Information

If email addresses are provided, always use the official email address of the Museum für Naturkunde, not a personal email address:

Example: Max.Mustermann@mfn.berlin

3. Multiple affiliations

If multiple affiliations need to be listed due to involvement with other research institutions, they should be listed in separate lines using a uniform font size. An exception is made if research results were exclusively produced at one institution.

The order of affiliations should be determined by the extent of the research contribution made at each institution for the specific publication. The Museum für Naturkunde should always be listed as one of the affiliations, as shown in the example:

¹ Museum für Naturkunde - Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science

² Humboldt University of Berlin

³ ...

4. Additional recommendations

4.1. Distinct Author Names - ORCID ID

To ensure permanent and unambiguous attribution of scientific publications, researchers are encouraged to use consistent name formatting. Additionally, it is recommended to create an ORCID ID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID²). This unique ID helps link publications and research achievements to an individual, remains valid even when changing institutions, and streamlines the publication process, as it is increasingly required by publishers and funders. Researchers retain control over the visibility and extent of their profile data.

The use of ORCID IDs is strongly recommended to facilitate individual attribution of scientific works and ensure clear connection to the institutional affiliation.

4.2. Institutional Identifiers

Some publishers use standardised identifiers for the unambiguous identification of institutions. If such an identifier is required and to ensure correct institutional attribution, the following identifiers can be used for the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin, with ROR-ID being the preferred ID where available:

ROR: [052d1a351](https://ror.org/052d1a351)³

ISIL: DE-MUS-813712⁴

ISNI: [0000 0001 2293 9957](https://isni.org/isni/0000000122939957)⁵

GND: [37657-7](https://explore.gnd.network/gnd/37657-7)⁶

Ringgold: [54206](https://ido.ringgold.com/search/results?simple=54206)⁷

VIAF: [146620974](http://viaf.org/viaf/146620974)⁸

Wikidata: [Q233098](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q233098)⁹

5. Funding Acknowledgements

For publications based on third-party funding projects, the funding organization should be listed in the "Acknowledgements" section, rather than in the affiliation. Many publishers provide standardized fields like "Funding Acknowledgements" to facilitate clear attribution. Precise identification of the funding agency also supports institutional transparency and simplifies potential future funding, especially for Open Access publications.

² The ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) is a non-proprietary alphanumeric code used to identify authors and contributors to scientific communication, as well as the ORCID website and services, to look up authors and their bibliographic output (and other information provided by the user).

³ ROR: <https://ror.org/052d1a351>

⁴ ISIL-URI: <https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-813712>

⁵ ISNI: <https://isni.org/isni/0000000122939957>

⁶ GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/gnd/37657-7>

⁷ Ringgold: <https://ido.ringgold.com/search/results?simple=54206>

⁸ VIAF-Permalink: <http://viaf.org/viaf/146620974>

⁹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q233098>

6. Support

For questions regarding the affiliation citation, creation of ORCID IDs, etc., the Coordination Office for Scientific Publishing is available. You can contact at: Publizieren.Bibliothek@mf.n.berlin.

Additional information and helpful resources can be found on our intranet page: https://mf.nlibef.sharepoint.com/sites/Wissenschaftsdatenmanagement_FB2_MfN/SitePages/Koordinierungsstelle-Wissenschaftliches-Publizieren.aspx.

7. Entry into Force and Duration of Validity

This guideline comes into effect upon its publication and will remain in force until further notice. The Museum für Naturkunde Berlin reserves the right to adjust this guideline as needed to align with current requirements.

Berlin, 27.05.2025

Director General

Berlin, 27.05.2025

Managing Director